

Discovering the Level of Acceptability on Health and Safety Protocols in the customer experience of Quick Service Restaurants in Dasmariñas, Cavite Branch

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7185229>

Published Date: 11-October-2022

Abstract: This research determined the level of acceptability on health and safety protocols in the customer experience of quick service restaurants in Jollibee Dasmariñas, Cavite branch. This study used a survey questionnaire as the main gathering tool. One hundred fifty-four (154) Jollibee consumers took part in it. Most of the participants strongly agree and believe that following health and safety protocols, by wearing a face mask, face shield, social distancing, by checking body temperature of the customer, plastic barrier in every table, plexiglass barrier in the front of the counter area, disinfecting every touch points of the customers, limited accommodation and limited employees, cashless and less contact payment can help to prevent viruses from spreading, but the participants strongly disagree that inside the fast food chain there is less probability of being infected by viruses. Most of the participants strongly believe that complying with health and safety protocols inside the store enhances their safety against the virus. Also, this study implies that most of the customers' experience was not affected by the implemented health and safety protocols.

Keywords: health and safety protocols, customer experience, quick service restaurants.

1. INTRODUCTION

Background of the study

Quick service restaurants or also known as fast food restaurants is a specific type of restaurant that offer excellent customer service and offer speed of service to their guests. In the Philippines fast food restaurants are a big help to Filipinos like students and simple workers that have minimum wages because some fast-food restaurants offer a budget meal that fits in people's financial capacity. Like in Jollibee they offer a value meal like Yum burger or Burger steak. Aside from the affordable price, many people eat in fast-food restaurants because of the unique taste of the food like chicken joy of Jollibee, burgers in McDonald and unlimited gravy in KFC.

Due to the pandemic, some fast-food restaurants were closed while some remained open but there are changes in their service because of the pandemic. Fast food restaurants are doing a health safety protocol like, no dining or minimum capacity of accommodation, wearing a face mask and checking the temperature of the customers.

This study aimed to know the acceptability of the compliance of health and safety protocol of the customer during their visit in three branches of quick service restaurant in Dasmariñas, Cavite located in Salitran, Bayan, and Walter Mart. This study will help the Government or management who implement the health and safety protocols during pandemic to know the feedback of the people who complied with the protocols if it is effective to prevent spreading the virus.

This study is a timely matter since Philippines is still facing pandemic due to COVID-19. This study will be helpful to the LGU of Dasmariñas Cavite in getting the feedback of their citizen regarding the health and safety protocols implemented in quick service restaurants. However, the feedback of the respondents will only base on their own experience and will not surely determine the effectivity of health and safety protocol implemented by the LGU in minimizing virus from spreading.

The difference of this study from other related study is that it will determine if the demographic profile: age and gender; have significant matter in customer's level of acceptability in health and safety protocols executed by quick service restaurants.

Department of the Interior and Local Government (DILG) and other Government sectors implemented health and safety protocols and laws for health and safety protocols. Penalties or sanctions can be imposed on violators under Republic Act 11332, also known as the Mandatory Reporting of Notifiable Diseases and Health Events of Public Concern Act, and the Local Government Code. According to Republic Act 10389, also known as the Recognizance Act of 2012, "a person who availed of bail on recognizance is turned over to a responsible member of the community who will ensure that he/she appears in court when called". Also, some violators that will violate health and safety protocols like not wearing a face shield and face mask are ordered to do community service and some are given warnings.

Conceptual Framework

This study highlights the level of acceptability in the implemented health and safety protocols of customers in three Quick Service Restaurant in Dasmariñas, Cavite Branch. This study also aimed to know if there is a significant relationship between the level of acceptability in the implement health and safety protocol inside the quick service restaurant and their experience. The conceptual framework will help the researcher to determine the significance of variables in the level of acceptability of customer to the health and safety protocols implemented in quick service restaurant.

Figure 1. Research Paradigm

Statement of the problem

This study aimed to know the acceptability of the compliance of health safety protocol for the customer during their visit in Jollibee fast-food chain in Dasmariñas, Cavite. Specifically, this study aimed to answer the following questions:

1. Demographic profile of Jollibee customer:

- Age
- Gender

2. What is the level of acceptability of Health and Safety Protocols to the customer experience of the Quick Service Restaurant in Dasmariñas?

2.1 Social distancing inside the quick service restaurant.

2.2 Wearing of faceshield while entering the quick service restaurant.

2.3 Wearing of facemask while entering the quick service restaurant.

2.4 Less Contact Payment transactions

- 2.5 Cash Less Payment transactions
- 2.6 Limited Dine in Customers
- 2.7 Plexiglas Barriers in the counter/cashier
- 2.8 Cleaning/sanitizing/disinfecting inside the food chain
- 2.9 Protective shield in every table.
- 2.10 Checking of temperature of every customer
- 2.11 Filling up contact tracing form
- 2.12 Limited number of employees on duty
- 2.13 Less probability of virus infection inside the food chain.
- 2.14 Following protocols enhances safety against the virus.
3. Does complying with health and safety protocols affects the experience of the customer inside the fast food chain?
4. Is there a significant relationship between the level of the acceptability of the implementation of health and safety protocols and the experience of the customer inside the fast food chain?

Statement of the Hypothesis

Ho: There is a significant relationship between the level of the acceptability of the implementation of health and safety protocols and the experience of the customer inside the fast food chain.

Ha: There is no significant relationship between the level of the acceptability of the implementation of health and safety protocols and the experience of the customer inside the fast food chain.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Local Literature

Philippines' number one fast-food chain known as Jollibee, strengthens its commitment in bringing joy to their customers while ensuring their safety through following the health and safety protocols. These safety protocols are proper social distancing, cashless payments and no touch transactions whether it is for take-out, delivery, drive-thru, order and pick up. Speakers are also installed and mics are used by the team members to minimize direct contact. Jollibee Food Corporation group also announced that they will give free vaccination for all its employees and household members.

In the national mobile survey conducted by Social Weather Stations in September 17-20, 2020, during the time where most of the places in the Philippines are under the Modified General Community Quarantine. The survey results showed that 79% of the Filipino respondents always use a face mask when going out of their houses, 67% of the respondent are always wash their hands several times a day, 60% of the respondents always follow the social distancing protocol, and 56% of the respondents always use face shield whenever they are riding a public transportation or going to different establishments.

Foreign Literature

According to the study of Hager E. et al (2020, July 29) majority of their respondents (61.6%) had a satisfactory knowledge about the virus. Also, majority (96%) of their respondents practiced social distancing and self-isolation however, only 36% follow all health protocols. Their study also states that the perception of most respondents (62.1%) was satisfied on the global efforts in preventing the virus to spread but, only 22% of the respondents were satisfied with their country handling the pandemic.

In line with the study of Girum, T. et al. (2020, November 23), quarantine, contact tracing, screening and isolation are effective measures in preventing the Coronavirus from spreading. Additionally, they state that controlling the transportation of the people enhanced the effectiveness of the quarantine. However, since the study shown that the disease can be asymptomatic, it is possible that the virus can spread unconsciously.

COVID-19's impact on destination safety and security procedures in the fast-food business. There are alternative ways that can be used in fast-food chains and businesses, based on health and safety restrictions must proliferate in the area. While it is critical to focus on medicines that reduce mortality, we must also consider the logistical challenges of safely and effectively delivering therapy while minimizing the risk of injury to all front liners and customers. In the mental health participants, self-reported measures of interprofessional collaboration and teamwork must collect.

In the study conducted by Pedersen M. and Favero, N. shows that some demographic factors: gender, age, race and political party affects the respondents' compliance in social distancing protocol. However, it is relatively poor compared with the individual attitudes and media used. American respondents appear that most of them complied with the social distancing protocol, but some individuals are non-compliant. In Stanford-led study (Moore et. Al. 2020) revealed that four in ten Americans were not complying with social distancing protocol however, the most common reason for not complying the protocol is due to work. While, other reasons are worries about mental and physical well-being (20.3%), belief that other safety measures such as hand washing is sufficient (18.8%), a wish to continue their everyday activities (13.9%), and lastly, is the belief that society is just overreacting (12.7%).

According the Ipsos' Consumer and Health and Safety Index, twenty-nine (29%) of the consumer do not buy in a retail shop if they knew it is not a compliant of health and safety protocols. In the survey conducted by Ipsos during the first week of July, revealed that consumers are more concerned in their safety than they were in May. Ipsos also states that consumer have highest trust on retail shop who have visible efforts in implementing and health and safety protocols. Ipsos also found that grocery is the most trusted by consumer. The most second trust is pharmacy and the lowest are wireless stores, fast-food chains and gas station.

Wearing a face shield provides another layer of protection against covid 19, reducing infection and transmission for other people. One of the studies conducted using both face mask and face shield provides better protection against transmitting viruses. A study by Bhaskar and Arun (2020) among community health workers in India, states that upon the implementation of wearing faceshield to their fifty (50) health workers who aided 118,428 COVID-19 patients in May 2020, none of the health workers were infected.

Wearing a face mask and doing social distancing are some of the health and safety protocols that provide protection and reducing for spreading the virus, but in some establishments transparent protective barriers are very important for their employees and for their customers also. It also protects employees for liquid droplets that coming from nose or coming from mouth like in cashier/counter area where employees talk to the customers.

Cashless transaction is highly encouraged by the World Health Organization (WHO) specially this pandemic, since cash is prominent in containing germs, bacteria and viruses. Michael Knight, assistant professor of medicine at the George Washington School of Medicine and Health Sciences, tells CNBC that cashless transaction is still useless if people will not wash and sanitize their hands carefully. However, cashless transaction is not required and people can still use cash payment but, people should always remember wash their hands after handling money especially before eating or touching their food to refrain people from getting infected by the virus.

3. METHODOLOGY

The researcher use the following methodology to gather the data needed in this study: research design, research locale, participants of the study, research instrument, data gathering procedure and data analysis.

Research design

This study employed descriptive research design to defined the current status of the identified variables. Moreover, this study was conducted to discover the level of acceptability of quick service restaurants health and safety protocols by customer experience in three Quick Service Restaurant Dasmariñas, Cavite Branch.

Research locale

The participants of this study are the customers of Quick Service Restaurant Dasmariñas, Cavite Branch during this pandemic. Participants are in the age of 18 years old to 65 years old in compliance in health and safety protocols. The average population of the Quick Service Resturant Dasmariñas, Cavite is 250. Using Slovin's formula, 154 sample size were computed with 5% margin of error. Therefore, total of 154 customers will be approach as the participant of the study in quick service restaurants Dasmariñas Cavite Branch

Research Sampling

This study chose a simple random sampling to a number of customer that visit Quick Service Restaurant Dasmariñas Cavite Branch. Simple random sampling gave the study a fair number of participants in each Quick service restaurants Dasmariñas Cavite Branch that has a capability to answer the survey questionnaire to avoid conflict.

Research Instrument

Customers and Quick service restaurants safety practices in Dasmariñas will be the subject of this research. This study used survey methodologies to know the level of acceptability of the customer in the implementation of health and safety protocol. It also demonstrated the link between the customer and their personal safety.

The instrument constructed by the researcher was divided into two section. The first section, focused on the demographic profile of the customer. The last section, assessed the customer's level of acceptability to the implemented protocols. The goal of the survey is to learn more about the demographics of quick service restaurants consumers as well as their opinions on the implemented health and safety policies inside the quick service restaurant.

Data gathering procedure

In order to determine the level of acceptability of Quick Service Restaurants Health and safety protocols by customer experience in quick service restaurants Dasmariñas, Cavite branch the researcher prepared a likert scale survey questioner for the target participants.

Before conducting the actual research, the survey questioner was validated and sign by the validator that shows approval that their data gathering tool is valid to conduct their study properly and the researcher can already conduct their research.

Lastly, a survey questionnaire has given to random Quick Service restaurant customers in three Dasmariñas Branch to gather data by explaining to them first the purpose of the study and their contribution or part on it. The survey questionnaire will be given through a google form, for the assurance of safety of the researcher and participants. After gathering all the data, the researcher analyzed all the data collected by their participants and interpret it.

Data analysis

The analyzed data that was conducted includes all the answers of the participants. The data was categorized based on the common answers by the participants to highlights the findings. Summarizing all the answers of the participants was a great help for the researcher in discovering the Level of Acceptability of Quick Service Restaurants Health and Safety Protocols by Customer Experience in Jollibee Dasmariñas, Cavite Branch.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

In this chapter, the data that had been collected were used to interpret the differences in response of the participants.

Gender

Figure 2. Gender

Figure 2 shows that sixty-two percent (62%) of the customers of Jollibee is Female and thirty-eight percent (38%) of the customers are male.

Demographic Age

Figure 3. Age of Jollibee Customers

Figure 3 shows that ninety percent (90%) of the customers of Jollibee are aged 18 to 39 years old and seven percent (7%) of the customers are between 40 to 64 years and three percent (3%) of the customers are aged 65 years old and above. This shows that adult age 18-39 years old are mostly the customers of Jollibee

Social Distancing inside the Food Chain

Figure 4. Social Distancing

Inside the fast food chain there are stickers that indicates a 1 meter apart to implement the social distancing between customers.

Figure 4 shows the perception of the respondents towards the help of preventing virus from spreading through social distancing wherein sixty-seven percent (67%) strong agree to it, sixteen percent (16%) agrees, fourteen percent (14%) are neutral, while two percent (2%) disagree, and only one percent (1%) strongly disagree. This data implies that most customer strongly believe that social distancing can help the prevention of virus from spreading.

Wearing Face Shield inside the Food Chain

Figure 5. Wearing Face Shield

Wearing a face shield ensures that water droplets carrying the virus can't directly contact the person wearing face protection. Using a face shield also serve as a continual reminder to refrain from touching one's face, eyes, or nose. This will stop any germs or water droplets on their hands from getting to their face and contaminating it.

Figure 5 shows the perception of the respondents towards the help of preventing virus from spreading through wearing face shield wherein forty-two percent (42%) strongly agree to it, sixteen percent (16%) agrees, twenty-four percent (24%) are neutral, while seven percent (7%) disagree, and eleven percent (11%) strongly disagree. This information suggests that the majority of users have a strong belief that using a face shield can help stop the spread of infections.

Wearing Face Mask inside the Food Chain

Figure 6. Wearing Face Mask

Wearing face mask prevents people from getting infected with the viruses because it keeps the germs comes to a person mouth and can aid in preventing respiratory droplets from a sick person from getting in others mouth.

Figure 6 shows the perception of the respondents towards the help of preventing virus from spreading through wearing face mask wherein sixty-nine percent (69%) strong agree to it, seventeen percent (17%) agrees, thirteen percent (13%) are neutral, while both disagree and strongly disagree are only one percent (1%). This data implies that most customers strongly believe that wearing a face mask can help the prevention of viruses from spreading.

Less contact payment transaction

Figure 7. Less Contact Payment

Contact less payment is implemented by the fast food chains through the use of tray plastic containers wherein customers put their payment in the payment tray, to limit the physical contact between the employee and the customer.

Figure 7 shows the perception of the respondents towards the help of preventing ourselves from acquiring virus through less contact payment wherein sixty-five percent (65%) strongly agree to it, fifteen percent (15%) agrees, seventeen

percent (17%) are neutral, while three percent (3%) disagree, and no one strongly disagree. This information indicates that the majority of customers have a strong belief that avoiding physical contact can help us avoid having infection from the virus.

Cash Less Payment Transaction

Figure 8. Cash less Payment

Cashless payments are done by online payment like Gcash, paymaya and card payment.

Figure 8 shows the perception of the respondents towards the help of preventing virus from spreading through cashless payment transaction wherein sixty-two percent (62%) strong agree to it, seventeen percent (17%) agrees, sixteen percent (16%) are neutral, while three percent (3%) disagree and only two percent (2%) strongly disagree. This data implies that most customers strongly believe that cashless payment transaction can help the prevention of viruses from spreading.

Limited Accommodation of Dine-in Customers

Figure 9. Limited Accommodation

Fast food chain accommodate thirty (30%) to fifty percent (50%) of customer to avoid customer being close to each other and to follow social distancing

Figure 9 shows the perception of the respondents towards the help of preventing virus from spreading through accommodating thirty percent (30%) to fifty percent (50%) capacity of dine-in customers wherein fifty-four percent (54%) strongly agree to it, twenty-two percent (22%) agrees, twenty percent (20%) are neutral, while only one percent (1%) disagree and three percent (3%) strongly disagree. This data implies that most customers strongly believe that accommodating thirty percent (30%) to fifty percent (50%) capacity dine-in customers can help the prevention of viruses from spreading.

Plexiglas Barriers in the counter/cashier

Figure 10. Plexiglas Barriers

A Plexiglas barrier in counter area in fast food chain is required because it can help to avoid water droplets that contains germs direct to the skin and nose, especially when the customer is ordering their foods in front of the service crew.

Figure 10 shows the perception of the respondents towards the help of preventing virus from spreading through Plexiglas Barriers in the counter/cashier wherein forty-four percent (44%) strongly agree to it, twenty percent (20%) agrees, twenty-three percent (23%) are neutral, while seven percent (7%) disagree and only six percent (6%) strongly disagree. This data implies that most customers strongly believe that Plexiglas Barriers in the counter/cashier can help the prevention of viruses from spreading.

Cleaning/sanitizing/disinfecting inside the food chain

Figure 11. Disinfecting

Cleaning, disinfecting and sanitizing is very important inside the fast food restaurants, it can help to kill the germs in every touch points of the customer, especially in tables and door.

Figure 11 shows the perception of the respondents towards the help of killing viruses through cleaning, sanitizing and disinfecting wherein eighty-five percent (85%) strongly agree to it, six percent (6%) agrees, seven percent (7%) are neutral, while both disagree and strongly disagree are one percent (1%). This data implies that most customers strongly believe that cleaning, sanitizing and disinfecting can help kill the viruses.

Protective shield in every table

Figure 12. Protective Shield

Plastic barrier in every table in fast food chain is required because it can help to avoid water droplets that contains germs direct to our skin and nose, especially when the customer is unmasked because they are eating.

Figure 12 shows the perception of the respondents towards the enhancing their safety against viruses through protective shield in every table wherein forty-three percent (43%) strong agree to it, twenty-two percent (22%) agrees, twenty-two percent (22%) are neutral, while eight percent (8%) disagree and only six percent (6%) strongly disagree. This data implies that most customers strongly believe protective shields in every table enhance their safety against the virus.

Checking each customer's temperature

Figure 13. Temperature Checking

Checking temperature of every customers enter the fast food chain is required. The normal body temperature is 36°F to 37.4°F if the customer is around 37.5°F above their body temperature, they rest above 5mins in the designated area in the restaurant and if the second times they check body temperature again and still 37.5°F their temperature they will not allowed to enter the store.

Figure 13 shows the perception of the respondents towards the ensuring that the customers is COVID-Free through checking temperature wherein sixty-eight percent (68%) strongly agree to it, twelve percent (12%) agrees, twelve percent (12%) are neutral, while, three percent (3%) are both disagree and strongly disagree. This data implies that most customers strongly believe that checking the temperature of every customer ensures that the customer is COVID-Free .

Contact tracing form in every customer

Figure 14. Contact Tracing Form

Contact tracing form will help the government to track down people that acquired and being danger by exposing in COVID 19

Figure 14 shows the perception of the respondents towards the contact tracing form in helping tracing people in case one of the customer is infected with covid wherein fifty-six percent (56%) strongly agree to it, seventeen percent (17%) agrees and neutral, while five percent (5%) disagree and strongly disagree. This data implies that most customers strongly believe that contact tracing forms are helpful.

Limited number of employees on duty

Figure 15. Limited Employee

Fast food restaurant with fewer personnel may help keep things from getting too crowded within the establishment so that employees can maintain their social distance.

Figure 15 shows the perception of the respondents towards the help of preventing viruses from spreading by limiting the employees on duty wherein thirty-one percent (31%) strongly agree to it, twenty-four percent (24%) agrees, twenty-seven percent (27%) are neutral, while twelve percent (12%) disagree and only six percent (6%) strongly disagree. This data implies that most customers strongly believe that limited employees on duty can help the prevention of viruses from spreading.

Less probability of getting infected with COVID 19 inside the fast food chain

Figure 16. Less Probability of Infection

Figure 16 shows the perception of the respondents towards the less probability of getting infected with COVID 19 inside the fast food chain wherein twenty-three percent (23%) strongly agree to it, ten percent (10%) agrees, twenty-eight percent (28%) are neutral, while ten percent (10%) disagree and twenty-nine percent (29%) strongly disagree. This data implies that most customers strongly disagree that inside the fast food chain there was less probability of getting infected with COVID-19.

Following protocols enhances safety against the virus

Figure 17. Following Protocols

Figure 17 shows the perception of the respondents where following protocols inside the fast food chain enhances safety against the virus wherein seventy-six percent (76%) strongly agree to it, fifteen percent (15%) agrees, seven percent (7%) are neutral, while one percent (1%) are both disagree and strongly disagree. This data implies that most customers strongly believe that following protocols inside the fast food chain enhances safety against the virus.

Experience of Customers amid Health and Safety Protocols

Figure 18. Experience amid Protocols

Figure 18 shows if the health and safety protocols implemented inside the fast food chain affects the experience of customers. Thirteen percent (13%) of the respondents said that protocols affects their experience inside the food chain while, eighty-seven percent (87%) of the respondents said that it does not affect their experience. This data implies that most of the customers' experience was not affected by the implemented health and safety protocols.

The data collected by the respondents signify that there is no significant relationship between health and safety protocols and experience of the customer inside the fast food chains.

5. CONCLUSION

This study determined the level of acceptability on health and safety protocols of the customer in quick service restaurant in Jollibee Dasmariñas, Cavite branch. Most of the customers of Jollibee are female and age eighteen (18) to thirty-nine (39) years old. Most of the customers in Jollibee are strongly agree that social distancing, wearing face mask and face shield can help the prevention of viruses from spreading. In mode of payment inside the quick service restaurant, most of the customer strongly agree that cashless and less contact payment prevent viruses from spreading. Most of the customers in Jollibee strongly believe that Protective shield in every table and Plexiglas barriers in the counter area enhance their safety against the virus. Most of the customer in Jollibee strongly believe that tracing form and checking of body temperature in every customers ensures the safety of every customer. Also, they strongly agree that limited accommodation and limited employees in quick service restaurant can help in preventing viruses from spreading as social distancing are being followed. They strongly agree that sanitizing, disinfecting and cleaning can help to kill and prevent viruses. Following health and

safety protocols are also strongly belief by the customers in enhancing their safety inside the food chain however, they strongly disagree that there is less probability of infection inside the quick and service restaurant. This study also shows that there is no significant relationship between the implementation of health and safety protocols and the experience of the customer inside the fast food chain.

6. RECOMMENDATION

The researcher provide the following recommendations based on their findings and conclusion:

For the future researchers, this study may serve as their starting point for future research and may aid future research that is related to it. It was strongly advised that they take their time collecting the data and studying it in order to ensure its validity and accurately ascertain the research study's conclusion.

For the Government Agency, this study can help different establishments better execute health and safety procedures.

REFERENCES

- [1] Caliwan, CL. (2021, June 1). DILG, DOJ ink memo on stricter health protocols' enforcement. Retrieved by <https://www.pna.gov.ph/articles/1142196>
- [2] English, T. (2020, June 9). Exploring the Options in Protective Counter Barriers for COVID-19. <https://www.inkonit.com/blog/exploring-the-options-in-protective-counter-barriers-for-covid-19/>
- [3] Girum, T. et al. (2020, November 23). Global Strategies and effectiveness for COVID-19 prevention through contact tracing, screening, quarantine, and isolation: systematic review. Retrieved by [https:// tropmedhealth.biomedcentral.com/articles/10.1186/s41182-020-00285-w](https://tropmedhealth.biomedcentral.com/articles/10.1186/s41182-020-00285-w)
- [4] Hager, E. et al. (2020, July 29). Knowledge, attitude, and perception towards the 2019 Coronavirus Pandemic: A bi-national survey in Africa. Retrieved by <https://journals.plos.org/plosone/article?id=10.1371/journal.pone.0236918>
- [5] Inquirer.net(2021, April). Alagang Jollibee: Safety and extra care for customers served daily. Retrieved from <https://www.google.com/amp/s/business.inquirer.net/320135/alagang-jollibee-safety-and-extra-care-for-customers-served-daily/amp>
- [6] Sieg, C. (2020, March 6). Can going cashless prevent coronavirus spread? Here's what the WHO wants you to know. Retrieved from <https://www.cnn.com/2020/03/06/what-you-need-to-know-about-handling-cash-amid-coronavirus-spread-who.html>

- [7] Social Weather Stations (2020, September 29). SWS September 17-20, 2020 National Mobile Phone Survey – Report No. 4: Large majorities still practice the Covid-19 Safety measures. Retrieved from <https://www.sws.org.ph/swsmain/artcldisppage/?artcsyscode=ART-20200929205756>
- [8] Pedersen, M. & Favero, N. (2020, May 22). Social Distancing during the COVID-19 Pandemic: Who are the present and future noncompliers. Retrieved from <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.1111/puar.13240>
- [9] Press Release (2021, June 4). Doh: face shields provide added layer of protection against COVID-19. Retrieved by <https://doh.gov.ph/press-release/DOH-FACE-SHIELDS-PROVIDE-ADDED-LAYER-OF-PROTECTION-AGAINST-COVID-19>
- [10] Wilson, M. (2020, July 22). Health, safety protocols remain most important factor for returning to a store. Retrieved by <https://chainstoreage.com/health-safety-protocols-remain-most-important-factor-returning-store>